

To Assess the Role of Mother's Knowledge Regarding Their Child's Health

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Child care is mostly the responsibility of mothers. Several studies have revealed that the mother's education has a positive impact on their knowledge and practice in child health matters. Child death due to malnutrition, vitamin deficiency and improper vaccination is most common in our society and these can be controlled by proper education of mothers about their child's health.

Objectives: The study was undertaken to assess the level of mother's knowledge regarding their child health, dietary pattern, prevalence of diseases and disorders among children and to improve all these awareness.

Materials And Methods: A community interventional study was conducted in selected areas of Chitradurga taluk. Scoring type multiple choice questionnaires was formulated and data collected from two rural and two affluent areas. After conducting the pre test and awareness, 10 days gap was given and later post test was conducted in the same population.

Results: Literate mothers are having more knowledge in dietary maintenance of children than illiterate mothers. And Urban locality mothers are having more knowledge in Dietary Maintenance and Up to date health check-up Of Children than rural locality mothers. Mother's knowledge about proper diet and vaccination are important to maintain their child's health.

Conclusions: Malnutrition, vitamin deficiency, improper vaccination and immunizations are caused by the lack of mothers' knowledge about the child health. Child death can be controlled to an extent by providing proper awareness to mothers.

Keywords: Child health, vaccination, immunization, knowledge

INTRODUCTION

It was observed that a good start at the beginning of the child's life helps to create an efficient person in the future society, because the first five-years in a child growth are a crucial period particularly for the development of the brain. [1] Mother's knowledge about child health is an important predictor of child's healthy growth. [2]

Nutrition is one of the basic requirements of any living organism to grow and sustain life. But the quality and quantity of nutrients necessary for normal growth and to keep an organism in good health during its life span varies with the age of the organism. Any major deviation in the nutrient intake either in quality or in quantity from its requirement can also affect growth and life span in a number of ways particularly in the later period/growth is more influenced by nutrition. [3] Malnutrition is the cellular imbalance between the supply of nutrients and energy and the body demand for them to ensure growth maintenance and specific function. It is worldwide health problem particularly in developing countries. Nutritional status is the condition of health of an individual as influenced by nutrient intake and utilization in the body. [4] Thus, good nutrition is essential for healthy, thriving individuals, families and a nation. Nutritionally educated mothers can bring up their children in a healthier way. [5]

Immunization is a high priority area in care of infants and children. High immunization rates have almost eliminated

many infectious diseases which used to decimate sizable of the population for countries. A number of deadly and disabling infectious diseases can be prevented by timely administration of vaccines when child is effectively immunized at the right age, most of these diseases are either entirely prevented or at least modified so that child suffer from a mild disease without any disability. [6] Uptake of vaccination services is dependent not only on provision of the services but also on other factors including knowledge and attitude of mothers and density of health workers. The opportunity costs (such as lost earnings or time) incurred by parents may also have an important impact on uptake. [7]

Exclusive breastfeeding (EBF) for the first six months of an infant's life is a cost effective intervention in saving children's lives and it is recommended by the World

Health Organisation. [8] Human milk is the ideal nourishment for infant's survival, growth, and development. Particularly in unhygienic conditions, however, breast milk substitutes carry a high risk of infection and can be fatal in infants. Breast milk contains all the nutrients an infant needs in the first six months of life. Exclusive breast feeding means that the infant receives only breast milk. Exclusive breast feeding in the first six months of life stimulates babies' immune systems and protects them from diarrhoea and acute respiratory infections. Exclusive breast feeding for the first six months of life is now considered as a global public health goal that is linked to reduction of infant morbidity and mortality, especially in the developing world. [9]

Mothers who are knowledgeable about general developmental sequences might be more likely to create an environment that is appropriate to their children's developing abilities, which in turn will support their children's cognitive and social advances. Hence, maternal knowledge can be conceptualized as indirectly affecting developmental outcomes

in children. Empirically, mothers of preterm infants who are more knowledgeable about infant development have been found to have babies with higher Bayley Mental Development Index and Physical Development Index scores. Mothers are differentially knowledgeable about progressions in children's play and variation among mothers in accuracy at ordering play activities predicts their play with their own children. [10]

Considering the above facts, the need for providing awareness regarding child's health care to mother's is very important in present scenario. Hence, we have come up with the title "To assess the role of mother's knowledge regarding their child's health".

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study design : This was a prospective study.

Study period : The study was conducted over a period of six months from 2017 to 2018.

Inclusion criteria:

- Mothers who are having children aged between 2 to 5 years
- Mothers who are working and non-working
- Mothers who are literate and illiterate.
- Mothers from both nuclear and joint family.

Exclusion criteria:

- Mothers who are having long term illness.
- Mothers who are above 35 years of age.

Ethical approval:

The study was approved by the Institutional Ethical Committee of Basaweshwara Medical College Hospital & Research Centre, Chitradurga.

Sources of data:

- Demographics of the patient.
- Questionnaire
- Interact with patient.

Study procedure:

- The study was carried out after getting the approval from Institutional Ethics

Committee. After taking the informed consent form, from the subjects after explaining the importance of the study and its benefits. Firstly, the study subjects were given a questionnaire where the answers will be collected and evaluated, which was the pre-test. After the pre-test, structured education has been given in the form of patient information leaflets and other media. After a gap of ten days, post-test was carried out on the same study subjects with the same questionnaire, which has been evaluated.

- The questionnaire was scoring type with multiple choice questions. Each correct question has been awarded one mark, whereas each wrong question has been given zero marks.

Statistical analysis:

- After the completion of the study, the data collected was entered into Microsoft Excel sheets and further analysis done by student paired “t” test in SPSS 24 version

RESULTS

Total no of 169 (Rural N=81, Urban N=88) subjects were enrolled in the study for 1st –visit, out of which 154 (Rural N=78, urban N=76) subjects were present in the 2nd visit. Hence we have selected the data of 154 subjects for further study analysis and remaining subjects were excluded from the study.

Out of 154 subjects, 134 were literate and only few of 20 were illiterate (figure 1). Among 134 literate subjects, schoolings were 58, PUC were 32 and graduates were 43 as per the demographics. In the study it was found that literated mothers are having more knowledge regarding their child's health. A total of 154 subjects, 45 were working and 109 were non-working (figure 2). Working women have knowledge about their child's health but they faces a problem “lack of time”. Through the study mother's knowledge was improved and awareness have been provided regarding child's health.

The results shows in Figure 3, Among study subjects from selected areas, the pre test score of mean (\pm SD) 2.458 (\pm 2.045), post test score of mean (\pm SD) 6.621 (\pm 1.451) and Paired T test value are 5.216 and 48.161 respectively (Table no.2). The p value for pre and post test is 0.004 which is significant and 0.001 which is highly significant.

Table 1:- Details of age wise distribution of mothers

Sl. no	Age group	Total	Percentage (%)
1	20-23	21	13.6
2	24-28	91	88.3
3	29-32	33	32.0
4	33-35	09	8.1
TOTAL		n=154	%=100

Figure 1: Details of education status of the mothers

Figure 2: Details of occupation status of mothers

Table no 2: Comparison of mean scores of knowledge of mother's knowledge regarding child health

Test	Mean	SD	T Value	P value, Sig
Pre test	2.458	2.045	5.216	0.004 (S)
Post test	6.621	1.451	48.161	0.001 (HS)

Figure 3: Comparison of mean scores of knowledge of mother's knowledge regarding child health.

DISCUSSION

“Children are our future” beyond the words it reflects the importance of child health. Maternal bond is the relationship between a mother and her child associated with pregnancy and child birth. And so mother's play important role in child health. Undesirable food habits and nutrition related practices, which are often based on insufficient knowledge, traditions, and taboos or poor understanding of the relationship between diet and health, can adversely affect a child's nutritional status.

A study entitled as “To assess the role of Mother's knowledge regarding their child's health” is prospective interventional study conducted in selected areas in Chitradurga taluk. Two rural and two affluent areas were selected for the study to assess the mother's knowledge regarding their child health, dietary pattern, disease and disorders among children which was found in line with Alkhazrajy LA ^[1] et al.

Our study aimed to improve the knowledge among mothers related to child health and the improvement in scores was found (mean pre and post test scores were 2.458 and 6.621 respectively), which sounds alike with the study conducted by Ansari M et al., and several others.

Our study aimed to find the relation between literacy of mother and dietary maintenance of the child and concluded that Literate mothers are having more knowledge in dietary maintenance of

children than illiterate mothers which was found identical with the study conducted by Levine RA et al.,

CONCLUSION

According to the analyzed results and from view of literature, the conclusions made are;

1. Male patients are more.
2. Patients of age > 60 are more.
3. Patients of body weight > 50 are more.
4. GFR <29 affected with anemia are more.
5. Anemia worsens with kidney function deteriorates.
6. Epoetin alfa, IV iron, Darbepoetin alfa, Blood transfusion are used in the management.

Anaemia is the most common complication of CKD and severity of anemia increases as CKD worsens and all patients had anemia. The optimum management of individual patients may vary in the clinical course of the disease and individual needs. Iron therapy is an important component of anemia management. Optimal correction of anemia, both erythropoiesis stimulating agents (ESAs) and iron supplementation are often required. ESAs such as Epoetin alfa (EPO) and darbepoetin are used to treat anemia. Uses of ESAs substantially reduce the need for transfusions and therefore are a first line of therapy for anemia of CKD.

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